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Abstract

This cross-sectional study investigated how bullying and peer victimization relate to the psychological adjustment of Bangladeshi adolescents. A sample of 250 high school students (eighth, ninth, and tenth graders) from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds in Dhaka completed the Bangla versions of the Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire and the Child Personality Assessment Questionnaire. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analyses. The results demonstrated a significant, positive correlation between bullying behavior and peer victimization. Furthermore, both variables correlated significantly with poorer overall psychological adjustment, indicating that higher involvement in bullying and victimization is tied to lower psychological well-being. Regression models confirmed both factors as significant unique predictors, collectively accounting for an additional 16% of the variance in adolescent adjustment. These findings highlight a critical need for targeted school-based psychosocial interventions and stakeholder sensitization.

Associations of Bullying and Peer Victimization with Adolescents' Adjustment

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The purpose of the current study is to investigate the associations of bullying and peer victimization with adolescents' adjustment. The sample in this cross-sectional design study consisted of 250 Bangladeshi adolescents (49.5% females, age: $M = 16.13$, $SD = 1.27$) from socioeconomically diverse background who were eighth, ninth and tenth graders. Participants completed two self-report measures namely Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire and the Child version (short form) of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire along with a Personal Information Form. Mean, Standard deviation, correlation and regression analyses were performed to analyze data. Pearson product moment correlations provided support for significant associations among the variables. More specifically, bullying behavior is significantly and positively correlated with peer victimization. Both bullying and peer victimization are significantly and positively correlated with adolescents' poorer overall psychological adjustment indicating that the higher bullying and the peer victimization the higher the adolescents' poorer overall psychological adjustment. Analyses further demonstrated that bullying and peer victimization are significant predictors of adolescents' psychological adjustment. Bullying and peer victimization explained additional 16% of the variance in adolescents' psychological adjustment ($F = 25.67$, $p < .001$). These findings highlight the importance of addressing bullying and peer victimization as both affect adolescents' overall psychological adjustment.

In recent years, serious consequences of bullying and peer victimization have caused great amount of attention from educators, school officials, researchers, practitioners, the media and the public (Phillips, 2007). According to the definition offered by Olweus (1993), bullying is the type of physical and/or verbal actions that a person (or group of persons) directs against a peer with an intention to cause harm to the victim, in hostile and repetitive fashion, abusing real or fictitious power. This popular definition nonetheless has come under criticism (e.g., Liu & Graves, 2011), leading to a newer definition of bullying: "bullying is when an individual uses goal-directed behavior that causes significant harm to another individual within the context of a power imbalance" (Volk, Dane, & Marini, 2014). So, central characteristics of bullying can be mentioned here as: (1) it is an intentional and (2) violent behavior, (3) which occurs over time, and (4) includes an imbalance of power between victim and perpetrator.

Bullying is generally described from an aggressor's perspective, while the term peer victimization is used for those who are targets of bullying (Card & Hodges, 2008). The definition of peer victimization which is another risk factor in that have long term effect on adolescent adjustment fundamentally encompasses a component of frequency in which the peer victimization must occur (Olweus, 2010). A peer victim is defined as a recipient of aggressive acts from one's peers over time (Olweus, 2001). Peer victimization is one of the most common problems that students experience during their school careers, especially in the middle and high school years. It is estimated that about one-third of youth are involved in some forms of victimization by peers (Nansel et al. 2001; Storch & Ledley, 2005). Youth who are victimized tend to be perceived as physically weaker and have fewer friends than those who are not victimized.

Previous research has demonstrated negative outcomes for students experiencing

peer victimization (e.g., Nakamoto & Schwartz, 2010). Among them, psychological distress appears to be the most salient outcome that victim experiences (Cole et al., 2010; Rudolph et al., 2011). Bullied children aged between 9-12 years old in Greece (Andreou, 2001) and South Korea (Schwartz et al., 2002) reported lower feelings of self-worth and academic functioning in comparison to their non-bullied peers. Researchers reported that those being exposed to bullying in adolescence, as either a bully or victim, had higher risks for poverty, poor mental and physical health as well as poor social relationships in adulthood (Wolke et al., 2013).

Adolescents experiencing bullying have an increased risk of physical, cognitive, and mental health issues (Moore et al., 2017). They also have heightened risk of suicidal ideations and even suicide attempts in extreme cases (Rigby & Slee, 1999). Bully-victims, who bully others and are also victimized themselves, have attracted growing attention by researchers and educational practitioners (Schwartz, 2000; Solberg, Olweus, & Endresen, 2007). Bully-victims are usually described as highly maladjusted having both externalizing (Veenstra et al., 2005) and internalizing problems (Ozdemir & Stattin, 2011).

In summary, the literature indicates that bullying and peer victimization have serious impact on the adolescents. Studies differ in their operational definition of bullying, therefore, clear generalizations about the nature and prevalence of bullying and peer victimization is challenging. Most of the studies are from the West and are not completely relevant to Bangladeshi context. In this background, the present study aims to find out the association among bullying, victimization, and adjustment among schoolgoing adolescents. There were some other specific objectives in this research. These are:

- to determine the relationship among bullying, peer victimization and psychological adjustment among adolescents;
- to determine whether bullying behavior and peer victimization significantly predict adolescents' adjustment.

Methods

Sample

The participants of the present study were from 3 high schools in Dhaka district of Bangladesh with an age range of 14 through 16 years (mean = 14.56, standard deviation = .67). The sample consisted of 250 high school students and they were selected by employing convenience sampling technique. Among the participants 58% were boys and 42% were girls; 42% were from eighth grade, 30.8% were from ninth grade and 27.2% were from tenth grade. Socio-economic status was self-reported as lower class (n = 37; 14.8 %), lower middle class (n = 40; 16 %), middle class (n = 137; 54.8 %), upper middle class (n = 26; 10.4 %) and upper class (n = 10; 4. %).

Design of the Study

Cross sectional survey design was used for the present study.

Measures

All participants in this research responded to the following self-report questionnaires along with the Personal Information Form (PIF):

Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (OBVQ). The Bangla translated version of Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (Uddin & Rahman, 2018) was used to measure adolescents' bullying and peer victimization. This questionnaire was originally developed by Olweus (1996). It is a self-report questionnaire composed of 23 items about bullying (bully scale) and 23 items about victimization (victim scale). Participants are asked to report the frequency with which this behavior occurred over the past month. For example: "I hit, kicked or pushed someone" (bully scale); "I was hit, kicked or pushed" (victim scale). Participants had to choose a response to each of the items from a four-category Likert scale that reflects the frequency of behaviors: (1) "Never", (2) "Once or twice a month", (3) "Around once a week", and (4) "Several times a week" (Olweus, 1996). The possible scale score for each scale ranges from a low of 23 to a high of 92. In the present study, Cronbach reliability scores for Bangla translated version of OBVQ were: $\alpha = 0.80$ (victim scale)

and $\alpha = 0.80$ (bully scale). However, the validity of the Bangla translated version of OBVQ has not been determined.

The Child version (short form) of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire (Child PAQ). The Bangla version of the Child PAQ Questionnaire (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005) was used to measure respondents' overall psychological adjustment. Participants responded to PAQ items on a 4-point Likert-type scale ranging from (4) "almost always true of me" to (1) "almost never true of me." The profile of a participant's overall self-reported psychological adjustment is achieved by summing the seven scale-scores after reverse scoring appropriate items. They include: (1) hostility/aggression; (2) dependence; (3) impaired self-esteem; (4) impaired self-adequacy; (5) emotional unresponsiveness; (6) emotional instability; and (7) negative worldview. The PAQ has been shown to have high reliability and validity in cross-cultural research (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005).

Some of the sample items of the Child PAQ are: "I think about fighting or being unkind" (hostility or aggression); "I like myself" (positive self-esteem); "I can compete successfully for the things I want" (positive self-adequacy); "It's easy for me to show my friends that I really like them" (emotional responsiveness); "I am cheerful and happy one minute and gloomy or unhappy the next" (emotional instability); "I think the world is a good, happy place" (positive world view). The possible scale score ranges from a low of 42 to a high of 210. Psychological maladjustment is indicated if the total PAQ score is at or above the scale midpoint 105. On the other hand, psychological adjustment is indicated if the total PAQ score is below the scale midpoint 105. A large body of evidence summarized in Uddin, Jasmine and Sultana (2007) indicates the measure to be reliable and valid for use in cross-cultural research. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of PAQ is .80 for the present study.

In addition, a Personal Information Form (PIF) accompanied the data collection instruments which elicited demographic, personal, and social information about respondent's gender, age, number of siblings, birth order, parental education, parental occupation, family

socioeconomic status, types of family etc. The questionnaires were administered during school hours, in the presence of two members of the research team who had been previously trained in the use of these instruments.

Procedure

Principals from purposively selected schools in Dhaka city have been communicated about the study through letter. The questionnaires were administered during school hours after principals agreed to have their school participate in the study. Participants and the teachers were informed verbally about the general purpose of the study in the classroom. They were asked to read the instructions provided with the questionnaire and to record personal information (age, sex, education, etc.) before answering the questions. It took 40 minutes on average to complete the total task. Ethical issues on this study were carefully handled and the participant's personal information was strictly protected. Participant's anonymity was ensured by assigning a code number written on the questionnaires.

Results

The data obtained from the surveys were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics including means, standard deviations, Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. The first research objective, determining the relationship among bullying, peer victimization and psychological adjustment among adolescents, was tested using simple correlations among the major variables in this study. The second research objective, determining whether bullying behavior and peer victimization significantly predict adolescents' adjustment, was examined using multiple regression. The dependent variable was adolescents' psychological adjustment. The obtained results are presented in Table 1 to through Table 3. All statistical analyses were carried out using the statistical program SPSS version 20.0.

The mean score for adolescents' bullying behavior was 30.44 (SD = 5.19) and mean score for adolescents' peer victimization was 34.05 (SD = 6.26). The mean score for adolescents' psychological adjustment was 95.61 (SD =

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Major Variables

Variables	Mean	SD	Possible Range	Actual Range
Bully	30.44	5.19	23 – 92	23 – 47
Peer Victimization	34.05	6.26	23 – 92	24 – 58
PAQ	95.61	15.64	42 – 210	63 – 172

Table 2. Correlations among Bullying, Peer victimization and Psychological Adjustment

Variables	1	2	3
1. Bully	1		
2. Peer Victimization	.52**	1	
3. Psychological adjustment	.40**	.30**	1

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3. Regression of Psychological Adjustment on Bullying and Peer Victimization (n = 250)

Predictors	B	SE	β	t	p
(Constant)	54.01	5.96		9.07	.000
Bullying	.99	.20	.33	4.86	.000
Peer Victimization	.33	.17	.13	1.97	.050

Adjusted $R^2 = .16$ ($F = 25.67$, $p < .001$)

Note. B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE= unstandardized standard error, β = standardized regression coefficient

15.64). Approximately, 25% ($n = 63$) of the adolescents had poor overall psychological adjustment (score > 105).

Table 2 shows correlations among bullying, peer victimization and psychological adjustment. It reveals that bullying behavior is positively correlated with peer victimization ($r = .52$, $p < .01$). Bullying is positively correlated with adolescents' poorer overall psychological adjustment ($r = .40$, $p < .01$). Again, victimization is positively correlated with adolescents' poorer overall psychological adjustment ($r = .30$, $p < .01$).

Table 3 indicates that both bullying and peer victimization are significant predictors of psychological adjustment. We can see that bully ($\beta = .33$, $p < .001$) and peer victimization ($\beta = .13$, $p < .001$) made significant unique contribution to the variance of adolescents' psychological adjustment. The value of standardized beta for bullying ($\beta = .33$) reveals that the increases of 1 unit in bullying increases 0.33 unit in adolescents' poorer psychological adjustment.

Similarly, the value of standardized beta for peer victimization ($\beta = .13$) reveals that the increases of 1 unit in peer victimization increases 0.13 unit in adolescents' poorer psychological adjustment. The model was significant and explained additional 16% of the variance in adolescents' psychological adjustment ($F = 25.67$, $p < .001$).

Discussion

The present study explored the associations of bullying and peer victimization with adolescents' adjustment. Some specific objectives of this study were: to determine the relationship among bullying, peer victimization and psychological adjustment among adolescents and to determine whether bullying behavior and peer victimization significantly predict adolescents' adjustment. To fulfill the purpose, data were collected from 250 high school children from 3 high schools in Dhaka district of Bangladesh administering self-report questionnaires. Results showed that, bullying is positively correlated with being a victim of bully. This finding is consistent with previous findings. Several studies have suggested the oscillation

of role between bully and victim (Slee, 1995; Swearer et al., 2001). This can be explained by social learning theory according to which the victims' bullying behaviors could be a socially learned behavior as a response to coping with bullying (Ma, 2001). Bullying research has also found that some of the most extreme victims are also among the most aggressive of bullies (Perry et al., 1988). The association between bullying and victimization can also be explained by the general strain theory which suggest that experiencing this type of strain like peer victimization makes the victim feel angry and frustrated, resulting in the desire to take action in order to alleviate negative emotions (Wallace et al., 2005).

The current study's findings are consistent with previous research findings regarding the positive association of bullying and victimization with adolescents' poorer overall psychological adjustment (Estevez et al., 2009; Young et al., 2006). Later, regression analysis was conducted assuming bullying and peer victimization to be predictor variables of psychological adjustment. According to our findings, bullying and peer victimization are significant predictors of adolescents' psychological adjustment. These findings corroborates with a study which found students to be aggressive toward others and victims show lower self-worth, higher levels of depressive symptoms, and more psychological problems (Undheim & Sund, 2010) A recent study in China using a sample of 14,536 children in Grades 6, 8, and 10 from public schools examined the correlation between bullying and psychosocial adjustment and found that perpetrating and being a victim of bullying are associated with poorer psychosocial adjustment (Zhang et al., 2019). Researches on victimization has focused primarily on identifying the consequences of being subjected to aggressive behavior and humiliations committed by peers (Estévez et al., 2014). Any type of aggression seems to negatively influence the victim's life, which is shown in behaviors like school or institute refusal, high levels of social anxiety, depressive symptoms (Cerezo, 2009) and feelings of loneliness and stress, as well as low self-esteem and low life satisfaction in general (Estévez et al., 2006; Gini et al., 2018).

Overall findings in this current study indicate that bullying and victimization are common among school-going adolescents, and it correlates with psychological adjustment. Nonetheless, both victims and bullies need appropriate psychosocial support in the form of screening for mental health needs, promoting healthy interactions with peers, opportunities to strengthen social-emotional skills and development of cognitive and academic skills. There is a need for sensitizing the peer group, teachers, parents, and administrators on tackling the issue of bullying and victimization. There is a good scope for school-based psychosocial interventions too. Life skill approaches and social-emotional learning programs can be useful in managing bullying by helping the children help themselves to regulate emotions, set and achieve positive goals, being empathetic, establish and maintain positive relationship, and make responsible decisions.

This study has specific limitations. We could not assess reasons for bullying and victimization. Another limitation of the study was that the study was conducted in three urban schools only. Hence, the findings may not be applicable for rural adolescents. Data in our present study was obtained using self-report measurement. So, there is a possibility that respondents may be influenced by social demands while responding, thus introducing bias into the results. Again we did not have a sufficiently large sample to explore important socio-demographic variables and other psychological characteristics that might have contributed to our findings. Future studies can address these issues.

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